

The Universe with Star Systems is Stable

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Network of Cosmic Systems

The network of cosmic systems (or cosmic web) refers to the universe with its star systems. A star system is a collection of members, where the member denotes a star and its planets including asteroids, comets, meteors (meteorites or meteoroids), etc.

Let us consider the abstract diagram (Figure 1) as the universe along with its star systems. In this diagram, each sphere denotes a star system like solar system. These systems in the universe are bound by gravitational attraction. The distance between any two consecutive systems in the universe remains unchanged in any direction; otherwise, the systems can collide with each other over the period of time. Therefore, the distances between systems of the universe are not possible to change. As a result, the universe with its star systems is stable [1].

Figure 1. The Universe with its Star Systems

Note that any object such as asteroid, comet, and meteor colliding with planets in planetary systems [1] should not be taken into account.

References

- [1] Annamalai, C. (2025) The Universe with its Systems is Stable. *Cambridge Open Engage*, Cambridge University Press. <http://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2025-3mpb9>.